

ART STUDIES

MUSICAL ACTIVITY AS A BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE QUALITIES OF THE PERSONALITY OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

This article examines the development of students' communicative skills through musical activities. The authors emphasize the role and place of music in the formation and development of fundamental personal skills such as communication. They analyze verbal and nonverbal forms of communication in the information field, the challenges of monitoring them, and the impact of students' musical activities on the emotional and psychological characteristics of their social interactions.

Keywords: musical activity, communication, students, music lessons, personality traits, listening to music, playing an instrument, emotional states.

The need to form communicative abilities and dialogue skills in the context of communication ("child - child") was first raised by N. M. Yuryeva [1], when organizing a joint activity (two children drawing a picture according to a model). Experimental studies of dialogical interactions of preschool children with each other in the context of joint activities showed the need to teach the child to build relationships.

Communicative competence (i.e., the ability to communicate) is considered as an ability that ensures the successful interaction of partners and the solution of communication tasks. This concept is defined as the ability to use language for pragmatic purposes, that is, it includes the processes of operating with the meanings of language signs - combining them according to certain rules and using them in communication, - it consists of linguistic and specifically communicative aspects.

A. M. Shakhnarovich [2] considered communicative competence as a general concept that includes language competence as a part of it. In his opinion, communicative competence includes the processes of working with the meanings of language signs - combining them according to certain rules and using them in communication (semantic, syntactic and pragmatic). The first two aspects constitute linguistic competence, linguistic competence is a special functional system, hierarchically organized, multi-component, consisting of elements and rules for their use. The «core» that combines and connects the components is the property of the elements to express some meaning in accordance with the rules, which is constantly developing.

Taking this into account, linguistic competence is the main component of communicative competence, which ensures its integrity and the formation of specific communicative skills. The difference between communicative competence (ability) and linguistic competence is the inclusion of pragmatic conditions in the semantic and syntactic structures of linguistic competence, which make speech acts successful, taking into account the correspondence and usefulness of the speaker, listener and context. V.V. Kazakovskaya [3] considers communicative competence as a functional system of abilities, and this system allows a person to effectively communicate in all types of communication, and is manifested in his speech acts. The author distinguishes two components of communicative competence: systemic-linguistic and specific communicative. By specific communicative competence we mean the presence of a model of speech acts in the speaker's mind and his ability to use them in dialogue and monologue.

According to K. Meng, who studied the communicative and verbal actions of older preschool children [4], it can be said that the language abilities of a child of this age are practically formed, however, the child can carry out purposeful collective actions (and related texts) only with the support of adults.

The results of the study show that there is a dialogic component in the structure of communicative competence. The framework of dialogic competence includes: knowledge of the structural scheme of a certain type of text, knowledge of the interactive nature of

communication, the ability to use the tools that implement it. In addition, for dialogic competence, the component of speaking skills is very important, which is speaking practice. So, by communicative dialogic skills we understand the skills associated with the use of language tools in real communication - in a dialogue.

According to A.G. Arushanova [5], as a child grows older, the share of verbal means of communication in communication with peers (compared to non-verbal means) increases compared to communication with adults. Starting from the age of three, the sphere of communication with peers becomes more verbal and encourages the use of speech rather than communication with adults. Around the age of six or seven, preschoolers' abilities for verbal communication increase sharply. By the age of six, communication with peers that is not based on a common visual situation becomes possible. A necessary condition for such communication is the establishment of eye-to-eye contact. According to M.A. Stepanova [6], speech ability plays a leading role in the development of a plot-role game as a means of communication; in connection with its development, children's speech activity also increases: the higher the level of development of the plot-role game, the more often, more and in more diverse forms schoolchildren resort to speech means during the game. As the game activity develops, its speech functions and corresponding forms change.

M.A. Stepanova's research materials showed that the forms and functions of speech skills can be developed not directly through the manner of speech, but indirectly - through play.

In the study of T.A. Repina [7], the dynamic nature of peer relations in the context of children's unsupervised activities within a group (primarily, play) is considered, communication is defined as a communicative activity, a process of establishing face-to-face contact. This communication is aimed not only at effectively solving the tasks of joint activity, but also at establishing personal relationships and getting to know another person.

The development of speech skills goes hand in hand with cognitive abilities. The enrichment of vocabulary, the improvement of word order occurs in each activity of the child (subject, artistic, movement, musical, compositional, and others), since these types of activity depend on speech. The integration of communicative, cognitive, aesthetic, and social development is realized when planning psychological and pedagogical work, when coordinating the tasks of students in parallel. The place of musical activity in this process is special.

In modern schools, a wide musical and aesthetic space is created, and students are involved in music not only through school, but also through additional educational institutions, through systematic and close monitoring of in-class, out-of-class and out-of-school forms of musical training. «Music is one of the most important means of educating each person», writes D.D. Shostakovich [8]. Music contributes to the well-being of society, contributes to the ethical process of social life. If people have highly developed emotional sides, then in difficult situations it allows them to turn to their

inner wisdom and find appropriate solutions. A person's perception of the world depends not only on the properties of the perceived object, but also on the psychological characteristics of the perceiver, his life experience, temperament, and state of mind at a given moment. And music, as one of the forms of reflecting reality, as well as one of the vital processes, is closely connected with the emotional sphere of a person.

The importance of musical education for the development of children, their emotional maturity, the formation of musical culture, artistic and creative outlooks on life, and the ability to build relationships within a team is considered in the works of D.B. Kabalevsky [9], B.M. Teplov [10], V.N. Shatskaya [11]. In this regard, T.V. Chelysheva, the author of the «Music» program, expressed the following opinion: the vitality of music is due to the need to accustom younger schoolchildren to musical art and is aimed at the following goals: personal, cognitive, communicative, social and aesthetic development of schoolchildren. Further, regarding communicative goals, he writes: «The communicative development of schoolchildren determines the following: the ability to listen, respect the opinions of other people; the ability to support the position of another person; readiness to conduct a dialogue; participation in the discussion of life and art phenomena that are important to a person; productive cooperation with peers and adults» [12], that is, all the characteristics of an individual that form the basis of his or her personality.

In the pedagogy of musical education, the problems of forming children's personal qualities through aesthetic education were addressed by L.V. Moiseeva [13], L.G. Dmitrieva [14], N.M. Chernovnenko [15], O.A. Apraksina [16], T.A. Kolysheva [17], R.A. Telcharova [18], N.V. Sokolova [19], N.A. Vetlugina [20] and others.

If we review the sources of musical education and educational literature, they indicate that there are two more types of communication that convey information that form the basis of communicative relationships during musical activity.

In order to make the learning process more effective as a condition for the development of personal qualities, it is necessary to study the patterns of musical education in class and out of class. In this regard, it would be appropriate to study the following:

- Features of the child's perception of music and its (perception) impact on the emotional state;
- The need to express one's feelings or share emotional impressions (or feelings) with other children (motivational factor);
- Ways in which the child expresses his/her feelings and aesthetic impressions;
- Selection of appropriate word combinations;
- Forms, style and manner of communication (question-answer, game, dialogue, monologue, etc.);
- Achieving the necessary (emotional-cognitive) communicative contact (contact);
- Development of cognitive and spiritual-moral qualities of the child's personality.

When solving the first task, the teacher should take into account the following - the child's specific perception of music depends on the characteristics of his age-specific psychological development. Here, one should not immediately rely on the teacher's own taste and extensive experience, because in some cases they may not «work».

Therefore, it is necessary to assess the psycho-emotional status of children in a specific situation, and not "generalized" children. In music lessons, communicative relationships between students usually arise quickly. Usually, children happily share their impressions of what they see, hear, and perceive.

In order for this process to proceed smoothly, the teacher should carefully select educational material that implements a certain type of musical activity: listening to music, singing, playing stringed instruments, musical-didactic games, etc., as well as a pedagogical repertoire that is accessible to students and appropriate for the type of activity.

It should be noted that all of the above types of musical activity affect the emotional state of children, and this, to a large extent, depends on the child's perception of music. For example, if we take two relatively different types of activity, then in this case the situational factor will play a decisive role in perception. (for example, listening to music and musical-didactic game).

Children's attention will be directed to the perception of the music itself when listening to music rather than to musical-didactic games, and during the game,

their attention will be directed not to the music, but to the procedural side of the game. Therefore, the teacher must be able to clearly distinguish the goals of using different types of activities.

Listening to music. The teacher selects a suitable piece of music to be listened to. It should be emotional, perhaps in content or program. Then, the teacher may give preliminary instructions so that the children perceive and react in a certain way.

Singing. Playing stringed instruments. The choice of each repertoire depends on the children's vocal capabilities and skills. The tessitura, range of the work should be narrow, and the work itself should be rhythmic, based on harmony, and modest in size. The form and genre should be suitable for children to perceive (song, march, etc.).

The second task: to encourage children to express and share their feelings with other children, not to leave them alone. This is a «motivating factor», which is determined and directed by the teacher himself, in order to form in the child, the need for self-expression. Why is this important? Because not all children react to what is perceived in the same way - in each class there are certain «activists» who are leaders, and there are also children who «keep quiet». Therefore, the task of the teacher is to «bring out» such children in the most transparent way and support them in expressing their opinions. In this case, it would be appropriate for the teacher to ask leading questions, give praise, and pay attention to some of the child's personal qualities (Table No. 1):

Table No. 1.

Tasks for the formation of communicative personal qualities of students in music lessons				
1	<i>Conditions for the formation of</i>	<i>Conditions for the formation of students' communicative personality qualities during music lessons</i>	<i>Types of musical activities</i>	
	<i>students' communicative personality qualities during music lessons</i>		Conditions for the formation of students' communicative personality qualities during music lessons	
			Conditions for the formation of students' communicative personality qualities during music lessons	<i>Singing. Playing a musical instrument.</i>
2	Peculiarities of a child's perception of music and its impact on the emotional state		The teacher selects an appropriate piece to be listened to. It should be emotional, perhaps in terms of content or program. Then, the teacher may give preliminary instructions so that the children perceive and react in a certain way.	
			The choice of each repertoire depends on the children's vocal abilities and skills. The tessitura and range of the work should be narrow, and the work itself should be rhythmic, based on melody and harmony, and small in size.	
3	The need to express their feelings or share their emotional impressions (or feelings) with other children (the striving factor)		Children should not remain passive and inactive, but should express their feelings or share their emotional impressions with other children. This «motivating factor» is determined and directed by the teacher himself,	
			The teacher's task is to «bring out» such children in the most accessible way and support them in expressing their opinions. It is necessary to ask leading questions, give praise, and pay attention to some of the child's personal qualities.	

	The ways in which the child expresses his feelings and aesthetic impressions		in order to form in the child the need for self-expression.	
4	Choose appropriate word combinations		Touching and alluding to relevant images and associations.	-
5	Communication forms, style and manner		question and answer, game, dialogue, monologue, etc.	Draw children's attention to the intonation, rhythmic features, etc. of music.
6	Achieving the necessary (emotional-cognitive) communicative connection (contact)		Actively discuss what was heard and received with other team members	Actively participate in joint performance rehearsals (singing and playing).
7	Development of the cognitive and spiritual and moral qualities of the child's personality		To convey "personal experience" (emotional state) to other children, comparisons, metaphors, epithets, etc.	Listening to the sounds of nature (songs of birds, animals, fairy-tale characters, etc.)

The next step in solving the problem of communicative personality traits of students in music lessons will be our third task, and the implementation of aspirational needs. It consists, so to speak, of three main parts: a/ the child's ways of expressing his feelings and aesthetic impressions; and b/ the selection of appropriate phrases and expressions; c/ forms of communication, style and manner (question-answer, game, dialogue, monologue, etc.)

In fact, as we have already said, when a child expresses his feelings and aesthetic impressions, he can do so in two different ways: verbal and non-verbal. The first (verbal) form, since it is based on language, cannot be considered dominant. Non-verbal communication can be one of the most expressive and expressive forms of expression, especially if children are less active - this observation is quite reasonable. More precisely, at first this form of communication is more convenient and acceptable for them, and later it can also turn into a form of speech.

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